

TIN-CATALYZED EPOXY VITRIMER MATRIX: AN APPROACH TO WASTE REDUCTION IN EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for epoxy fibre-reinforced composites raises significant environmental concerns due to the large amounts of waste produced. This study investigates the use of vitrimers - polymers that combine the durability of thermosets with the reprocessability of thermoplastics- to reduce such waste. Our approach involves substituting traditional, irreversible epoxy matrices with inherently reversible epoxy vitrimer systems.

We present a novel vitrimer system synthesized from a conventional epoxy monomer, a carboxylic acid curing agent, and an organotin catalyst. The material is synthesized via a simple one-pot process using easily accessible raw materials, to enhance its suitability for industrial adoption. The catalyst's thermal properties contribute to the generation of a robust network that resists degradation during reprocessing. In addition, vitrimerization is used to convert a cured, traditional epoxy material into a vitrimer, highlighting the potential for waste valorization. Finally, an efficient chemical recycling method is presented for epoxy vitrimer composites, showcasing the potential for material recovery in composite applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Epoxy fibre-reinforced composites are widely used in industries such as aerospace, automotive, and construction. However, they generate a lot of waste, largely due to the use of epoxies as matrix materials. The underlying issue lies in their chemistry: traditional epoxy resins, which belong to the thermosetting class of polymers, form irreversible, covalently crosslinked networks [1]. While this structure provides them excellent thermomechanical properties -at a reasonable cost and with great versatility-, it also makes them extremely difficult to recycle or repair, and impossible reshape. As the market for these composites continues to grow, a surge in waste is expected, amplifying environmental concerns and underscoring the urgent need for innovative solutions [2].

Vitrimers, a new class of dynamic polymers discovered in 2011 [3, 4], have emerged as a promising solution for designing materials that generate less waste. Above a critical topology freezing temperature (T_v), their networks can rearrange without losing covalent connectivity thanks to accelerated associative bond exchange reactions, allowing them to flow and fully relax stresses [5, 6]. When used as matrices, vitrimers enable the development of recyclable, repairable, weldable, and reshapable composites [7-14]. However, their heavy reliance on expensive or commercially unavailable raw materials has so far hindered their adoption by industry [15-31].

In this work, we demonstrate the potential of epoxy vitrimers to address both future and existing epoxy composite waste. First, we present a recyclable epoxy matrix that maintains its thermal and dynamic properties after recycling, offering a viable strategy to reduce future waste generation. We also present a simple chemical recycling method that enables the recovery of fibres with clean surfaces within two hours. Furthermore, we show that fully cured, irreversible epoxy thermosets can be converted into reprocessable vitrimers through a vitrimerization process [32], providing a promising route for valorising existing epoxy waste.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Matrix. The formulation was based on D.E.R. 332 diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, M_w 177.0 g/mol, Sigma-Aldrich) as diepoxy monomer and sebacic acid (SA, M_w 172.17 g/mol relative to the epoxy group, Sigma-Aldrich) as curing agent. Monobutyltin oxide (Sn, M_w 208.8 g/mol, Tokyo Chemical Industry) was employed as catalyst. Chemical structures are presented in **Table 1**.

Reinforcement. 3K twill weave carbon fibre fabric (200gsm, Enhanced Composites) was used to reinforce the matrix.

Role	Chemical compound	Chemical structure
Monomer	Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA)	
Curing agent	Sebacic acid (SA)	
Catalyst	Monobutyltin oxide (Sn)	

Table 1: Chemical structures of the raw materials used

2.2 Sample preparation and recycling

Preparation and recycling of epoxy samples. Overall, four matrix materials were developed and compared (see **Figure 1**). First, two initial epoxy systems were synthesized: a vitrimer (v), as well as a conventional thermoset (TS) prepared without any catalyst. Both systems were then reprocessed to produce a recycled vitrimer (Rv) and a vitrimerized thermoset (vTS). The formulations were prepared using a 1:1 ratio of epoxy to carboxylic acid functional groups, with the catalyst added at 5 % molar equivalent (meq.) relative to the epoxy.

The two initial epoxy systems (v and TS) were prepared by mixing SA powder with DGEBA using an overhead stirrer at 60 °C and 250 rpm for 24 hours. For the vitrimer system (v), the catalyst (Sn) was then added to the mixture, followed by an additional 30 minutes of stirring. After mixing, the formulations were degassed at 90 °C for 4 hours. The curing process was completed by heating the samples for 8 hours at 145 °C, followed by 8 hours at 160 °C. The recycled vitrimer (Rv) was prepared by cryo-grinding the original vitrimer (v) into a powder, followed by compression molding at 200 °C for 1 hour, under approximately 5 MPa of pressure. In case of the vitrimerized vitrimer (vTS), the conventional thermoset (TS) was cryo-ground together with the catalyst, added at 5 % meq. relative to the epoxy group, and then processed using the same compression molding conditions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Impact of matrix reprocessing on its thermal properties

The impact of matrix reprocessing on the thermal properties of the materials was evaluated using DMA, with a focus on the glass transition temperature (T_g) and rubbery storage modulus (see **Figure 2**).

First, a comparison between the original vitrimer (v) and thermoset (TS) reveals that the vitrimer has a higher T_g and rubbery plateau (measured at $T = T_g + 30$ °C). This is likely caused by an increase in crosslink density, resulting from the addition of the tin catalyst to the network, expected to accelerate curing and promote branching reactions in this diepoxy-diacid vitrimer systems [33]. This is consistent with the rise in storage modulus at high temperatures, implying that the material continues to undergo reactions that increase its crosslink density. Moreover, comparing the peak heights of tan delta for v and TS reveals that TS exhibits a higher peak, indicating greater molecular mobility within its network [34, 35]. This is expected for non-catalyzed diacid-diepoxy systems, where polyaddition reactions between epoxy and carboxylic acid groups likely dominate [36, 37], resulting in the formation of long, linear hydroxyester chains [33, 38].

It is interesting to note that the recycled vitrimer (Rv) shows a 6 % reduction in T_g and a 20 % lower rubbery storage modulus values compared to v, along with a slightly higher tan delta peak height. This suggests a material with greater flexibility, which is unexpected for a recycled material.

When comparing the original (TS) and vitrimerized (vTS) thermosets, an increase in T_g and rubbery plateau, as well as a decrease in tan delta peak height, is observed for vTS. The introduction of rigid domains into the network could be responsible for this effect, correlating with the visible shoulder at low temperatures indicative of microstructural variation [39]. Such heterogeneity could originate from inadequate integration of the catalyst into the network, leading to the formation of non-dynamic thermoset regions, further characterized by shorter chains than those of TS due to potential chain scission occurring during reprocessing. Still, despite these noticeable differences, the T_g and storage modulus values indicate that the vitrimerization process doesn't compromise such thermomechanical properties.

Figure 2: DMA of conventional thermoset (TS), original vitrimer (v), recycled vitrimer (Rv), and vitrimerized thermoset (vTS). Temperature-dependent evolution of the storage modulus and tan delta.

TGA results (see **Figure 3**) further support the preserved thermal stability of the vitrimer system after reprocessing: the original (v) and recycled (Rv) vitrimers exhibit nearly identical thermal degradation profiles. Specifically, their initial degradation temperatures (T_{onset}), defined as the temperatures at which 5 % weight loss occurs, are 328 °C and 331 °C, respectively. Their peak degradation temperatures (T_{max}), corresponding to the maximum rate of weight loss determined from the derivative thermogravimetric (DTG) curves, are 414 °C and 415 °C. And their residual weight at 800 °C falls within the range of 15 - 17 %. While the vitrimerized thermoset (vTS) exhibits very

similar behaviour, a slight distinction is observable, with its T_{onset} , T_{max} , and residual weight reaching 345 °C, 423 °C, and 17 %, respectively. This subtle increase in thermal stability might be attributed to a higher proportion of irreversible -hence more stable- bonds in the network compared to the non-vitrimerized vitrimers.

In contrast, the conventional thermoset (TS) exhibits a notably higher initial degradation temperature (approximately 60 °C above that of the vitrimer systems) highlighting the commonly observed trade-off between thermal stability and reversibility. A lower onset of degradation in vitrimers is indeed expected, given their ability to flow at elevated temperatures.

Overall, the similarity in thermal degradation profiles among v, Rv, and vTS indicates that neither the recycling process nor vitrimerization significantly affected the thermal resistance of the matrix. In particular, the nearly identical behavior of v and Rv confirms that the material remained largely unaffected by the recycling process, which aligns with the DMA results and underscores the excellent thermal robustness of the vitrimer system. In addition, the comparable thermal stability of Rv and vTS reinforces the potential of vitrimerization as an effective approach for thermoset recycling, enabling material recovery without loss of thermal performance.

Figure 3: TGA curves for conventional thermoset (TS), original vitrimer (v), recycled vitrimer (Rv), and vitrimerized thermoset (vTS).

3.2 Impact of matrix reprocessing on its dynamic properties

Stress relaxation experiments were conducted to assess the dynamic behavior of the vitrimer systems and evaluate the effect of reprocessing on their flow properties. In such tests, a constant strain is applied, and the decrease in stress over time is monitored. At 200 °C, the original (v) and recycled (Rv) vitrimers exhibit full stress relaxation, while the vitrimerized thermoset (vTS) shows slightly reduced relaxation due to the presence of non-exchangeable covalent crosslinks. In contrast, the conventional thermoset (TS) shows negligible relaxation, as expected given the absence of dynamic bond exchanges (see **Figure 4**).

The characteristic stress relaxation times were determined using the Maxwell model of stress relaxation [5]. The results show that the recycled vitrimer (Rv) relaxes at a rate nearly identical to that of the original vitrimer. For instance, at 200 °C, both systems exhibit a relaxation time of 10 minutes. This highlights that the recycling process preserved the dynamic behavior of the vitrimer network. Interestingly, the vitrimerized thermoset (vTS) displays notably slower stress relaxation kinetics. At 200 °C, the relaxation time of vTS is 23 minutes -more than twice that of v and Rv. Stress relaxation in vitrimers is primarily governed by the rate of dynamic exchanges [5, 34, 40], namely, in this case, transesterification reactions between hydroxyl and ester groups [41, 42]. Therefore, the slower stress relaxation observed in vTS indicates that the dynamic exchanges occur at a reduced rate. A greater proportion of irreversible bonds may account for this, by increasing the network's rigidity and the

average distance between dynamic moieties. Such a phenomenon could result from insufficient or uneven catalyst incorporation, a common challenge in vitrimerization [32, 43].

In summary, the results confirm that an irreversible thermoset can be transformed into an inherently recyclable material through vitrimerization. In the case of Rv, the findings highlight that the recycling process has minimal impact on the dynamic properties of the vitrimer. However, the slower stress relaxation observed in vTS implies that the vitrimerization process impacted the material's dynamic properties, possibly due to suboptimal incorporation of the catalyst into the network. To improve this, reducing the particle size of the thermoset powder or increasing the compression molding time could be considered [43].

Figure 4: Stress relaxation behaviour at 200 °C for conventional thermoset (TS), original vitrimer (v), recycled vitrimer (Rv), and vitrimerized thermoset (vTS).

3.3 Impact of composite recycling on fibre quality

The chemical recycling process (see **Figure 5**) enabled to separate the fibres from the vitrimer matrix (v) after only 10 minutes of immersion in diethylene glycol (diEG). The solvent's active role in dynamic transesterification exchanges allows the vitrimer matrix to depolymerize, thereby enabling the separation of fibres from the matrix [4, 44]. Both the temperature of the process and the amount of solvent used significantly influence the rate of depolymerization.

It is worth noting that the dissolved matrix could be recovered and reused to produce a new chemically recycled vitrimer matrix. However, in practice, complete removal of the solvent remains a challenge. The recovered material typically retains residual solvent, resulting in a plasticized matrix with considerably higher flexibility than the original due to a higher amount of hydroxyl groups. While this may restrict its suitability for some applications, it could also offer opportunities in others where enhanced flexibility is desirable.

Figure 5: Pictures of composite chemical recycling: a) Preparation of CFRv sample, consisting of the original vitrimer (v) reinforced with carbon fibres. b) Sample immersion in diethylene glycol (diEG) at 180 °C. c) Fibres easily separated from the depolymerized matrix after 1 hour of immersion. d) Fibre recovery for characterization.

The surface quality of the recovered fibres was evaluated using SEM after immersion in diEG for two different immersion durations: 10 minutes and 2 hours (see **Figure 6**). SEM images reveal that, after 10 minutes, matrix residues are still clearly visible on fibre surface, whereas after 2 hours, these residues have substantially disappeared, indicating a more complete matrix depolymerization. To further assess fibre cleanliness and confirm the preservation of fibre quality, TGA will be conducted on the recovered fibres.

Overall, these results illustrate the strong potential of vitrimer-based matrices to facilitate composite recycling and enable the recovery of high-value materials.

Figure 6: SEM images of recycled fibres after 10 minutes (left) and 2 hours (right) of recycling, showing a visual comparison of their quality.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The vitrimer system developed in this work was synthesized using a conventional epoxy monomer, the biobased and affordable sebacic acid as curing agent, and an organotin catalyst. The resulting material exhibited a glass transition temperature of 51 °C and a characteristic stress relaxation time of 10 minutes at 200 °C. The synthesis process, combined with the material's thermal robustness and the accessibility of its raw materials, supports its industrial relevance. First, it was shown that this vitrimer system can be recycled without compromising its thermal and dynamic performance. After recycling, the material largely retained its T_g, rubbery plateau, thermal stability, and stress relaxation behavior, highlighting its excellent reprocessability. Additionally, a chemical recycling method was implemented to recover fibres from vitrimer-based composites. After two hours of immersion in diethylene glycol at 180 °C, SEM images revealed clean fibre surfaces. To tackle existing composite waste, the vitrimerization of fully cured conventional epoxy thermosets was also explored. The process successfully converted a thermoset into a reprocessable material, able to flow and significantly relax stresses at high temperature. A slight increase in T_g, rubbery plateau, and thermal stability was noticed compared to the original vitrimer, possibly due to the introduction of irreversible bonds into the network. While no loss of thermomechanical properties was observed, the results reveal a notably slower stress relaxation response -at least twice as slow as the original vitrimer-, which could be attributed to a higher proportion of irreversible bonds in the network, in line with our DMA and TGA results. This phenomenon could be explained by an inadequate integration of the catalyst into the network.

Overall, this study demonstrates the potential of epoxy vitrimers as a more sustainable alternative to conventional epoxy matrices for reducing composite waste. By substituting traditional, irreversible epoxy systems with dynamic, reprocessable vitrimer networks, this approach addresses both future and existing composite waste streams. Ultimately, this research aims to support a more environmentally responsible composite industry.

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